

Design and Molecular Analysis of Edaravone for the Treatment and Reduction of Oxidative Stress in Pulmonary Disorders

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Objectives of the Proposal

- To investigate the mechanism of action of edaravone in the treatment of respiratory issues.
- To evaluate the stability and molecular interactions of edaravone with proteins and lung tissues.
- To determine the therapeutic potential of edaravone in reducing inflammation and oxidative damage in lung tissues.
- To propose clinical applications and future perspectives for the use of edaravone in treating respiratory problems.

Statement of the Problem

The drug Edaravone, commercially known as Radicava and Radicut, began its clinical studies under the code name MCI-186 in 1987 by Mitsubishi Chemical Industries. In 2001, Mitsubishi Tokyo Pharmaceuticals received approval for Edaravone for the treatment of neurological symptoms, daily activity disorders, and functional impairments due to acute cerebral infarction, with the condition that it must be administered within 24 hours of symptom onset. Unlike existing anticoagulant and antiplatelet drugs, Edaravone can be used not only in cerebral thrombosis but also in cerebral embolism. It is the first drug in Japan to be confirmed effective based on the internationally used modified Rankin scale and was approved for treating acute ischemic stroke in Japan in 2001 [10, 5].

In 2005, Edaravone was designated as an orphan drug for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and later approved for ALS treatment in Japan and South Korea in 2015. It was then approved by the FDA in May 2017 and Health Canada in October 2018. The oral suspension formulation of Edaravone was approved by the FDA in May 2022 and by Health Canada in November 2022. Edaravone was approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of ALS in May 2017 and became available to U.S. healthcare providers from August 2017.

Edaravone was initially designated as an orphan drug by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) on June 19, 2015, and was under regulatory review in Europe. However, the drug's manufacturer, Mitsubishi Tanabe Pharma Corporation, withdrew the marketing authorization application (MAA) for Edaravone from the European market on May

24, 2019, following the Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP)'s request for a long-term study to demonstrate the drug's long-term efficacy and safety. Edaravone has also been investigated for other conditions, such as Alzheimer's disease, neuropathic pain, and ischemic-induced nerve damage [7].

A pivotal, randomized, controlled clinical study conducted in Japan showed that Edaravone slows the rate of functional loss in ALS. The drug is administered intravenously in clinical centers, infusion centers, or at home [4].

Edaravone is known as a powerful antioxidant capable of inhibiting free radicals and reducing oxidative stress. It acts as a free radical scavenger and neuroprotective agent with antioxidant properties. The molecule exists in three tautomers [3] and functions by scavenging free radicals to remove lipid peroxides and hydroxyl radicals, which appears to primarily reduce oxidative damage in motor neurons [2].

Edaravone is a member of the 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives class, chemically named 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. It is a white crystalline powder with a melting point of 129.7°C, readily soluble in acetic acid, methanol, or ethanol, and slightly soluble in water or diethyl ether. The molecular formula of Edaravone is $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O$, with a molecular weight of 174.20. Edaravone is available as a clear, colorless liquid in a sterile injectable solution for intravenous infusion (IV) in polypropylene bags containing 30 mg of Edaravone in 100 ml of isotonic solution. Inactive ingredients include L-cysteine hydrochloride hydrate, sodium bisulfite, sodium chloride for isotonicity, and phosphoric acid and sodium hydroxide for pH adjustment to 4.17 [11].

Despite preclinical and clinical studies, there is still a need for a more precise understanding of the molecular mechanisms of Edaravone's effects in reducing oxidative stress and treating pulmonary diseases. Molecular simulations can help us explore these mechanisms [13, 9, 14]. GROMACS software is one of the most powerful molecular simulation tools, capable of modeling interactions between drug molecules and biological targets with high accuracy. Using this software, we can simulate the potential effects of Edaravone on various molecules and cells and gain a better understanding of its mechanisms of action [13].

Detailed analysis and molecular modeling of Edaravone's effects can lead to the development of more effective drugs and improvements in existing treatment methods for chronic pulmonary diseases. This could help reduce the burden of these diseases and improve patients' quality of life. Given the significant role of oxidative stress in pulmonary diseases and the proven protective effects of Edaravone in preclinical and clinical studies, designing and performing molecular analysis of this drug using GROMACS software is of high importance. These analyses can enhance our understanding of molecular mechanisms and support the development of new drugs for treating and reducing pulmonary oxidative stress.

Necessity of the Study

Oxidative stress is a significant factor in the progression of pulmonary diseases such as Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) and pulmonary fibrosis. Oxidative stress, caused by excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), can lead to cellular damage and inflammation. Edaravone, as a potent antioxidant, has the capability to inhibit ROS and RNS, which could be effective in reducing oxidative stress and treating related diseases. Due to its ability to scavenge free

radicals and reduce lipid peroxidation, Edaravone is considered a promising therapeutic option for pulmonary diseases [14, 1].

Molecular simulations can enhance our understanding of the molecular mechanisms of Edaravone's effects. These methods allow researchers to examine precise interactions between molecules and design better drugs [8, 15]. Studies have shown that Edaravone can reduce the production of oxidative products and diminish inflammatory responses after temporary ischemia. These properties suggest that Edaravone may also be effective in treating pulmonary diseases [6, 12].

Background of the Study

A study by Watanabe et al. (1994) demonstrated that Edaravone, through inhibiting lipid peroxidation and reducing ROS production, can mitigate damage caused by cerebral ischemia. These findings indicated that Edaravone is capable of effectively scavenging free radicals. Aoki et al. (2002) showed that Edaravone can decrease the production of oxidative products and reduce inflammatory responses following temporary ischemia in mouse brains. Kikuchi et al. (2010) reported that Edaravone acts as a strong inhibitor of peroxy radicals and peroxynitrite, and these properties make it a potential treatment for oxidative damage. Zhang et al. (2005) utilized molecular simulations to study Edaravone's interactions with free radicals, showing that the drug can effectively inhibit peroxy radicals. Lindahl et al. (2001) developed the GROMACS software for molecular simulations, which can be used to investigate the molecular mechanisms of drug effects, including those of Edaravone.

Research Methodology

First, the molecular structure of Edaravone will be collected using unique identifiers such as PubChem (CID: 1886) and DrugBank (DB06894) and converted into formats suitable for simulation. Software tools like ChemDraw or Avogadro will be used to convert the structural files into appropriate formats. Then, using the GROMACS software, the simulation system, including molecules, water, and ions, will be set up, and the necessary input files will be generated. At this stage, PDB files will be converted into GRO and TOP formats, and charges and hydrogens will be added to the structures.

After preparing the system, an initial molecular dynamics simulation will be conducted to optimize energy and structural stability. During this simulation, structural changes and molecular interactions will be analyzed using GROMACS tools. The simulation results will be analyzed based on temperature, pressure, and structural stability, with all stages and results documented and analyzed. A final report including the simulation results and related analyses will be prepared for publication and presentation at conferences. For this research, GROMACS will be used for molecular dynamics simulations, and tools like CHARMM-GUI will be utilized for system preparation. The models used will include the molecular structure of Edaravone and other target molecules, along with structural data and simulation parameters.

Expected Results

The expected results from the design and molecular analysis of Edaravone for treating and reducing pulmonary oxidative stress include identifying and confirming the molecular mechanisms of the drug's effects on reducing oxidative stress in lung tissues. It is anticipated that molecular dynamics simulations will provide more detailed information about Edaravone's interactions with target molecules and its impact on biochemical pathways related to oxidative stress. Additionally, the research is expected to show that Edaravone can reduce free radical production and inhibit oxidative processes in lung tissues, potentially leading to the development of more effective treatments for respiratory diseases. The obtained analyses could enhance our understanding of the drug's mechanism and assist in designing new and optimized formulations to reduce oxidative stress in pulmonary diseases.

References

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